

LITERATURE REVIEW ON DEVELOPING VIETNAMESE LANGUAGE FOR 3–6-YEAR-OLD THAI ETHNIC PRESCHOOLERS THROUGH LITERATURE APPRECIATION IN KINDERGARTENS

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Abstract: Developing the Vietnamese language for ethnic minority children at the preschool level is a vital task to improve educational quality and create a foundation for learning at subsequent levels. For Thai ethnic preschoolers, the use of their mother tongue in daily life causes many difficulties when accessing and using Vietnamese in a learning environment. This article provides an in-depth review of research related to developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers and analyzes the role of literature appreciation as an effective language education tool in kindergartens. The review results show that organizing activities to access stories, poetry, folk verses, and idioms not only contributes to expanding vocabulary and training listening-speaking skills but also helps children form interest and confidence when using Vietnamese. On that basis, the article clarifies the significance of utilizing literary works in developing Vietnamese for Thai ethnic preschoolers and suggests research directions and the application of appropriate measures in preschool education practice.

Keywords: Vietnamese language, Vietnamese language development, 3–6-year-old preschoolers, Thai ethnic group, literary works, preschool education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Language plays an especially important role in the comprehensive development of preschool children. Through language, children can communicate, express their needs, emotions, and thoughts, and perceive the world around them. Language is not only a communication tool but also a means to help children acquire knowledge, develop thinking, and form personality. According to the Preschool Education Program issued by the Ministry of Education and Training, language development is one of the important educational areas aimed at helping children form and develop the ability to listen, speak, enrich vocabulary, develop expression skills, and use Vietnamese appropriately in daily communication [1].

According to Nguyen Anh Tuyet, language is an important means to help children perceive the surrounding world, develop thinking, and form personality. Through language, children can express their thoughts, feelings, and needs, as well as acquire experiences from the living environment. Developing language for preschool children not only helps them communicate better but also creates a prerequisite for intellectual development and learning ability at subsequent educational levels [2]. Additionally, Le Thu Huong argues that organizing language development activities for preschoolers needs to be implemented in rich, flexible forms suitable for children's psychological characteristics. Teachers need to create many opportunities for children to listen, speak, exchange, and communicate in learning activities as well as daily life to improve

their ability to use Vietnamese [3]. When children participate in diverse, attractive, and appropriate activities, they become bolder in communication, while their vocabulary and expression skills develop naturally.

In kindergarten educational activities, literature appreciation is considered one of the effective ways to develop language for children. Dinh Hong Thai asserts that through stories, poems, idioms, and folk verses, children are exposed to language that is rich in imagery, emotion, and high artistic value. From there, children have the opportunity to expand their vocabulary, train listening-comprehension skills, develop expression skills, and form aesthetic feelings. Simultaneously, literary works also help children develop imagination, memory, and the ability to retell story content according to their own understanding [4].

For ethnic minority children in general and 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers in particular, developing the Vietnamese language is especially significant. In family and community environments, children often use their mother tongue, Thai, in daily communication. Therefore, when coming to kindergarten, many children face difficulties in listening, understanding, and using Vietnamese. Their Vietnamese vocabulary is limited, their expression is not yet clear, and they are often shy about communicating or mix their mother tongue during communication. This significantly affects their participation in learning and communication activities within the preschool educational environment.

Reality at many kindergartens in areas with a high population of Thai ethnic children shows that enhancing Vietnamese for children has received attention, but the effectiveness remains low. One of the reasons is that the organization of language development activities, especially literature appreciation, is sometimes monotonous, not truly attractive, and has not created many opportunities for children to use Vietnamese actively. Therefore, researching appropriate measures to develop Vietnamese for Thai ethnic children through literature appreciation activities is very necessary.

Stemming from the theoretical and practical bases mentioned above, researching the development of Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers through literature appreciation in kindergartens is significant in both theory and practice. The research results will contribute to proposing appropriate measures to improve the efficiency of Vietnamese language development for Thai ethnic children and support preschool teachers in organizing language education activities more effectively.

2. RESEARCH CONTENT

2.1. Research methods

To review the issues regarding the development of Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers through literature appreciation in kindergartens, the study uses a combination of several research methods to collect and process information scientifically, specifically as follows:

+ Theoretical research method:

This method is used to understand and systematize the theoretical basis related to the topic. During the research, the researcher collects and reads documents such as books, textbooks, scientific research works, and documents on preschool education, especially those related to language development and enhancing Vietnamese for ethnic minority children. On that basis, the study analyzes and synthesizes scientific perspectives on the language development characteristics of preschoolers, the role of Vietnamese for ethnic minority children, and the significance of literature appreciation in developing language for children.

+ Pedagogical observation method:

This method is used to monitor and record manifestations of the Vietnamese language usage ability of 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers while they participate in learning activities and daily life at kindergarten. Specifically, observation focuses on literature appreciation activities such as listening to stories, reading poetry, answering questions, and participating in exchanges and communication in Vietnamese. Through observation, the researcher can recognize the level of children's understanding and use of Vietnamese, their ability to comprehend story content, their ability to answer questions, and their boldness in communication.

+ Analysis and synthesis method:

After collecting information from theoretical and practical documents, the study analyzes, compares, and synthesizes data to draw necessary remarks and conclusions related to the research problem. This method helps systematize the collected information and clarify the current status and the role of literature appreciation in developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers.

2.2. Basic concepts

2.2.1. Vietnamese language and Vietnamese language development

Vietnamese is the national language and the official means of communication of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam. Linguistically, Vietnamese belongs to the Austroasiatic language family, the Viet-Muong group, with a phonological system rich in tones, a diverse vocabulary, and a flexible grammatical structure. Vietnamese is not only a communication tool but also a means for people to think, acquire knowledge, and transmit the cultural values of the nation [5].

In the field of education, Vietnamese plays an especially important role as the primary tool helping children access learning activities and form personality. For preschoolers, using Vietnamese helps them communicate with teachers, peers, and the surrounding environment, thereby developing cognition and social skills.

Vietnamese language development is understood as the process of forming and perfecting children's language skills, including: developing phonetics, vocabulary, grammar, and communication skills. During this process, children are trained in correct pronunciation, expanding vocabulary by theme, knowing how to use sentences appropriate to the communication context, and forming the ability to listen, understand, and express their own thoughts and feelings.

At the preschool age, Vietnamese development is also linked to familiarization with writing, helping children recognize letters and form pre-reading and pre-writing skills. Activities such as storytelling, poetry reading, language games, conversations, or experiential activities all contribute to promoting children's language development. Therefore, developing Vietnamese in preschool education is significant, creating a foundation for children to prepare well for Primary school [2].

2.2.2. Developing Vietnamese for ethnic minority children

Developing Vietnamese for ethnic minority children is the process of organizing purposeful and planned pedagogical impacts to help children form and improve their ability to use Vietnamese in communication and learning. For ethnic minority children, Vietnamese is often approached as a second language; therefore, developing Vietnamese does not stop at expanding vocabulary but also includes training listening, speaking, standard pronunciation, using grammatically correct sentences, and coherent expression.

According to the Ministry of Education and Training, enhancing Vietnamese for preschool children in ethnic minority areas aims to help children have enough capacity to use Vietnamese to complete the preschool education program, be ready for Grade One, and study effectively at subsequent educational levels [6].

This process needs to be implemented by building a rich linguistic environment, organizing diverse communication activities, and integrating Vietnamese into play, daily life, and educational activities such as storytelling, poetry reading, and language games. Simultaneously, respecting and utilizing the children's mother tongue is also considered an important supporting factor helping children access Vietnamese more effectively.

Thus, developing Vietnamese for ethnic minority children is a process that helps children form and perfect their ability to use Vietnamese as a tool for communication and learning. This contributes to ensuring educational equity and improving educational quality in ethnic minority areas.

2.2.3. Language development for preschoolers

Language development for preschoolers is the process by which children receive, acquire, and use language in communication with adults, peers, and the surrounding environment through daily activities, play, and learning. This is a highly social process linked to children's cognitive, emotional, and behavioral development.

According to V.I. Lenin: "Language is the most important means of human communication," affirming the special role of language in social life as well as in the development of each individual.

Vietnamese linguists also argue that language is both a means of communication and a tool for thinking, reflecting the level of human cultural and social development [5]. Nguyen Lai (1997) argues that children's language development is strongly influenced by the communication environment, in which the family and the school play a decisive role [7].

In preschool education, language development is seen as one of the central tasks of the educational program. According to the Preschool Education Program issued by the Ministry of Education and Training, the goal of language development for children is to help them comprehend, communicate effectively, pronounce correctly, expand vocabulary, and form a prerequisite for learning to read and write in primary school [1].

Especially at the age of 5–6, children are already capable of using relatively complete sentences, retelling events, and expressing their thoughts. Therefore, language development at this stage is significant in preparing children for Grade One.

2.2.4. *Enhancing the Vietnamese language*

Enhancing Vietnamese is the process of systematically organizing educational measures to support children in developing the ability to use Vietnamese, especially for ethnic minority children or children with limited Vietnamese proficiency.

This process includes activities such as expanding vocabulary, training standard pronunciation, developing listening-speaking-comprehension skills, and the ability to express oneself in Vietnamese. Simultaneously, enhancing Vietnamese also aims to build a rich and friendly Vietnamese communication environment, providing children with many opportunities to use the language in learning and daily activities.

Through this, children will communicate confidently, participate boldly in activities, and possess a solid language foundation when entering grade One [6].

2.2.5. *Familiarizing children with literary works*

The activity of familiarizing children with literary works is the process of organizing children to interact with, listen to, and perceive literary works such as poetry, stories, folk verses, idioms, fairy tales, etc., that are suitable for the psychological and physiological characteristics of preschool children.

Through this activity, children not only understand the story content but also perceive the beauty of words, thereby forming a love for the Vietnamese language and literature. At the same time, literature appreciation activities also help children expand their vocabulary, develop communication skills, and foster aesthetic perception capabilities.

The forms of organizing literature activities in kindergarten are very diverse, such as: expressive reading, storytelling using pictures, puppet storytelling, role-playing characters, open-ended conversations, or recreating the story content. These forms help children participate actively, increase interest in learning, and develop language naturally [4].

2.2.6. *Vocabulary and vocabulary development for children*

Vocabulary is the total set of words that an individual knows and is capable of using in communication and thinking. In linguistics, vocabulary is considered the word bank of a language or an individual [9].

Developing vocabulary for children is the process of expanding the quantity of words and improving the ability to understand as well as use words in different communication situations. Through educational activities such as chatting, storytelling, reading poetry, and observing objects and phenomena, children gradually learn the names, characteristics, and properties of surrounding things and phenomena.

This process not only helps children increase their vocabulary but also contributes to developing cognition and thinking abilities.

2.2.7. *Literary works*

A literary work is an artistic creative product using language, in which the writer, through a system of artistic imagery, reflects life and expresses their thoughts and feelings [10].

For preschool children, literary works often have close-to-life content, clear imagery, and pure language, which are suitable for the psychological and physiological characteristics of children. These works help children develop language, imagination, aesthetic emotions, and moral values.

2.2.8. *Thai ethnic group*

The Thai ethnic group is one of the 54 ethnic groups of Vietnam, living mainly in northern mountainous provinces such as Son La, Dien Bien, Lai Chau, Yen Bai, Nghe An, and Thanh Hoa. The Thai people have a long-standing history of residence in the Northwest region and possess a unique culture with traditional values such as Xoe dance, folk songs, festivals, and folk tales.

The language of the Thai people belongs to the Tay-Thai language group, which is different from Vietnamese; therefore, many Thai ethnic children, when starting kindergarten, are not yet proficient in using Vietnamese for communication.

2.3. Role and significance of developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers

2.3.1. Role of developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers

Developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers plays a very important role in the preschool education process because Vietnamese is not only a communication tool but also a tool that helps children perceive the world around them and develop their thinking. For ethnic minority children, especially Thai ethnic children, the mother tongue is usually used primarily in the family and community. Therefore, when coming to kindergarten, children may encounter many difficulties in listening, understanding, and using Vietnamese in communication and learning.

Enhancing Vietnamese helps children gradually form and develop basic language skills such as listening, understanding, speaking, and expressing in Vietnamese. When the ability to use Vietnamese is improved, children will be more confident in communicating with teachers and peers, while also boldly participating in learning and play activities at school. This contributes to creating a positive communication environment, helping children develop social skills and form appropriate communication habits.

Besides, Vietnamese also plays the role of an important tool that helps children develop cognition and thinking. Through using Vietnamese in learning activities such as listening to stories, reading poetry, chatting, or participating in other educational activities, children have the opportunity to expand their vocabulary and understand the meanings of objects, phenomena, and the relationships between them. Thanks to this, children gradually form logical thinking abilities, memory, comparison, and generalization skills, contributing to promoting the intellectual development of children.

Additionally, developing Vietnamese also helps children effectively access educational content in the preschool curriculum. Most educational activities in kindergartens are organized in Vietnamese; therefore, if children do not yet understand or use this language proficiently, receiving educational content will encounter many difficulties. When Vietnamese is enhanced, children can better understand the requirements and instructions of the teacher, thereby participating actively in educational activities and improving learning efficiency.

2.3.2. Significance of developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers

Developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers not only has significance for language development but also contributes importantly to the comprehensive development of children. First, enhancing Vietnamese helps children have a solid language foundation to prepare for entering the primary level. At this educational level, Vietnamese is the main language used in teaching and learning. If children do not have a good Vietnamese foundation, they will face many difficulties in acquiring knowledge, especially in subjects that require reading comprehension and linguistic expression skills.

Furthermore, developing Vietnamese also helps children increase their ability to integrate into the educational and social environment. When children have good communication skills in Vietnamese, they will find it easier to exchange with teachers, peers, and those around them. This not only helps children become more confident but also creates conditions for children to expand social relationships and participate actively in collective activities.

In addition, developing Vietnamese through appropriate educational activities, especially literature appreciation activities, also helps children be exposed to language rich in imagery and emotion. Through stories, poems, folk verses, etc., children expand their vocabulary, practice coherent expression skills, and develop their imagination. Simultaneously, literary works also contribute to emotional education and foster moral and aesthetic values in children.

For ethnic minority children, developing Vietnamese also has the significance of ensuring equal learning opportunities and narrowing the educational gap between regions. When Thai ethnic children are equipped with the ability to use Vietnamese well, they will have more opportunities in learning, accessing knowledge, and developing themselves in the future.

In summary, developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers is of great significance to the language development, thinking, communication, and learning process of children. This is also an important foundation that helps children confidently integrate into the educational and social environment, while creating a prerequisite for the comprehensive development of children in subsequent stages.

2.4. Literature review on developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers through literature appreciation in kindergartens.

In the context of fundamental and comprehensive reform of education and training in Vietnam today, preschool education is identified as the first educational level in the national education system, playing an important role in forming and developing the initial foundations of human personality. At this stage, children are developed comprehensively in terms of physical, cognitive, linguistic, emotional-social, and aesthetic aspects, creating a solid foundation for the learning process at subsequent levels. Among the developmental areas of preschool children, language development, especially developing Vietnamese for children aged 3-6, is considered an important task with great significance for children's cognitive, communicative, and learning processes [9].

The age of 3-6 is the stage when children's language develops strongly. During this period, children gradually expand their vocabulary, step-by-step perfect their sentence structures, and improve their verbal expression abilities. Children begin to know how to use language to communicate with adults and peers, expressing their thoughts, feelings, and needs, as well as participating in learning and play activities. Language is not only a means of communication but also an important tool helping children develop thinking, memory, imagination, and form social relationships. Therefore, developing Vietnamese for children aged 3–6 plays an important role in helping children speak correctly, clearly, and coherently, while contributing to the development of the child's thinking, emotions, and personality [11].

However, in current preschool education practice, the Vietnamese language development of 3–6-year-old children still has many limitations and is not uniform. Some children still face difficulties in pronunciation, their vocabulary is still limited, their expression is not yet coherent, or they are not yet bold and confident in communication. Especially for children in ethnic minority areas, developing Vietnamese encounters even more difficulties because children often use their mother tongue in daily communication. The difference between the mother tongue and Vietnamese can affect the child's ability to pronounce, understand word meanings, and use Vietnamese sentences [13].

Besides, socio-economic conditions, the linguistic environment in the family, and the teacher's methods of organizing language development activities are also factors affecting the effectiveness of Vietnamese development for children. In the context of implementing the Preschool Education Program according to a child-centered orientation, teachers need to organize educational activities suitable for the psychological and physiological characteristics of children, creating many opportunities for children to communicate, experience, and use Vietnamese in many different situations [10].

Among the educational activities in kindergarten, the activity of familiarizing children with literary works is considered an effective path helping to develop language for children. Through listening to stories, reading poetry, and participating in activities that recreate the works such as retelling the story, role-playing characters, or exchanging about the content of the work, children are exposed to a Vietnamese language that is rich in imagery and emotion. This helps children expand their vocabulary, develop listening-comprehension skills, and practice verbal expression skills [12].

For Thai ethnic preschoolers, literature appreciation activities are even more significant in enhancing Vietnamese. Through literary works that are age-appropriate and close to the children's lives, children not only expand their Vietnamese vocabulary but also practice listening-speaking skills, develop communication abilities, and foster emotions, ethics, and aesthetics. Therefore, researching the theoretical basis for developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers through literature appreciation activities is necessary, contributing to proposing appropriate educational measures to improve the efficiency of language development for preschoolers in ethnic minority areas.

2.4.1. Global research

In many countries around the world, the issue of language development for preschool children has been of interest to many scientists and researched very early. Research works all affirm that the preschool stage (3–6 years old) is an important period for forming and developing vocabulary, communication abilities, as well as language expression capacity of children.

Many researchers such as A.M. Borodich, A.M. Sokhin, and E.I. Tikheyeva have had research works on methods for developing speech for preschool children. A.M. Borodich also emphasized the role of storytelling and story-reading activities in developing language for children. He argued that: *"Through listening to stories and retelling the story, children not only expand their vocabulary but also develop their expression and linguistic thinking"* [11].

Furthermore, A.M. Sokhin affirmed that organizing children to participate in literary activities such as storytelling, reading poetry, and role-playing according to story content is an effective method to develop speech for preschoolers. According to him: *"Literary activities help children develop coherent speech, while forming communication abilities and emotional expression"* [12]. The authors argue that organizing children to become familiar with literary works such as stories, poetry, folk tales, folk verses, etc., plays an important role in developing vocabulary, training listening-comprehension skills, and forming coherent expression skills for children.

In her research, E.I. Tikheyeva emphasized that providing children with regular exposure to literary works helps them expand their vocabulary, develop emotional expression abilities, and form communicative language. She also proposed many forms of organizing activities such as reading stories for children to listen to, storytelling, conversations based on story content, letting children act in plays, or retelling the story from memory. According to E.I. Tikheyeva, familiarizing children with literary works helps children expand their vocabulary, develop expression skills, and form coherent speech. She argued that: *"Literary works are an important means to develop speech for preschool children, helping children acquire language rich in imagery and expression"* [13].

In modern research, Ageliki Nicolopoulou also pointed out that storytelling and story-acting activities in preschool classrooms have a positive impact on the language development of children. She argued that: *"Storytelling and story-acting activities support children's language development and narrative competence"* (Activities of telling and re-acting stories help develop language capacity and storytelling capacity of children) [14].

Besides, modern preschool education researchers also affirm that activities of telling stories and reading books to children not only help develop language but also contribute to developing imagination, thinking, and social communication abilities of children. Through literature appreciation activities, children are exposed to language rich in imagery and emotion, thereby helping them expand their vocabulary and improve expression skills.

From the above studies, it can be seen that scientists all agree that literature appreciation is one of the important means helping to develop vocabulary, expression skills, and communication capacity for preschoolers. However, these studies mainly focus on children in general and have not yet deeply researched the development of Vietnamese for ethnic minority children, especially Thai ethnic children in Vietnam. Therefore, researching measures to develop Vietnamese vocabulary for Thai ethnic preschoolers through literature appreciation is necessary.

2.4.2. Domestic research

In Vietnam, the issue of language development for preschool children in general and developing Vietnamese for preschoolers in particular has received the attention of many researchers in the field of preschool education. Research works have affirmed that language plays an important role in the comprehensive development of children, while serving as a tool helping children communicate, perceive the world around them, and form personality.

According to Nguyen Anh Tuyet, language holds an especially important position in the psychological development process of preschool children. The author argues that: *"Language is an important means for children to communicate with everyone around them and is a tool for children to perceive the world"* [8]. Therefore, the development of Vietnamese for children needs to be implemented through many different educational activities to create conditions for children to communicate and use language frequently.

From a pedagogical perspective, Le Thi Anh Tuyet emphasizes that literature appreciation activities are of important significance to the language development of children. According to the author: *"Literary works such as poetry, stories, and folk verses help children be exposed to language rich in imagery and emotion, thereby contributing to expanding vocabulary and developing expression skills"* [15]. This shows that organizing children to become familiar with literary works not only helps them develop language but also contributes to forming aesthetic emotions and nurturing the child's soul.

Consistent with the above perspective, Phan Thi Thu Hien also affirms the role of literary activities in developing speech for preschoolers. The author argues that: *"Through activities of storytelling, reading poetry, and conversations based on the content of literary works, children are trained in listening-comprehension skills, expand their vocabulary, and develop coherent speech"* [16]. Thus, it can be seen that using literary works in preschool education is one of the effective paths to develop language for children.

In the current context of educational innovation, the issue of developing Vietnamese for ethnic minority children is receiving more and more attention. Nguyen Thi Phuong Thao argues that: "*Developing Vietnamese for ethnic minority preschool children is an important condition helping children to be able to study and integrate well with the general education environment*" [17]. This shows that increasing activities that help ethnic minority children access and use Vietnamese is an important task of preschool education.

From the above studies, it can be seen that domestic scientists all affirm the important role of developing Vietnamese for preschool children, especially ethnic minority children. However, research works mainly focus on developing language for preschool children in general or research ethnic minority children on a broad scale, and have not yet deeply researched measures to develop Vietnamese vocabulary for Thai ethnic preschoolers through literature appreciation activities within the specific conditions of kindergartens in Nghe An province. Therefore, researching this topic is necessary to contribute to supplementing the theoretical and practical basis for improving the quality of Vietnamese language education for Thai ethnic children at the preschool level.

3. CONCLUSION

Developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old preschoolers, especially ethnic minority children like Thai ethnic children, is an important task in preschool education today. Vietnamese is not only a means of communication but also a tool helping children perceive the world around them, develop thinking, and form initial learning skills. Enhancing Vietnamese for children right from the preschool age will create a solid foundation for children to be confident when entering the primary level and subsequent educational levels.

Through a review of domestic and international research documents, it can be seen that many scientists have affirmed the important role of language development for preschool children. Research works all emphasize that literature appreciation activities such as storytelling, reading poetry, listening to stories, role-playing according to the work's content, etc., are among the effective means helping children expand their vocabulary, train listening-comprehension skills, and develop coherent speech. Through literary works, children are exposed to language rich in imagery and emotion, thereby forming expression skills and developing linguistic thinking naturally.

For Thai ethnic children, developing Vietnamese through literature appreciation activities is even more significant. Literary activities not only help children expand their Vietnamese vocabulary but also create opportunities for children to communicate and express their thoughts and emotions in a friendly and close learning environment. Simultaneously, literary works also contribute to fostering emotions, moral education, and aesthetic development for children.

However, through the review of research works, it can be noted that most previous studies mainly focused on language development for preschool children in general or researched ethnic minority children on a broad scale. In-depth research on developing Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers through literature appreciation activities, especially in the context of preschool education in specific localities, is still not abundant.

Therefore, continuing to research and propose appropriate measures to develop Vietnamese for 3–6-year-old Thai ethnic preschoolers through literature appreciation activities is necessary. The research results will not only contribute to supplementing the theoretical basis for the field of preschool education but also possess practical significance in improving the effectiveness of organizing language development activities for ethnic minority children, contributing to improving the quality of preschool education in ethnic minority areas today.

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